

Supplemental Figures

Human enhancers harboring specific sequence composition, activity, and genome organization are linked to the immune response

Fig. S1 Silhouette plots of k-means clusters. Silhouette plots for clusters obtained using the k-means clusterization algorithm for $k = 2$ (a), $k = 3$ (b), $k = 4$ (c), and $k = 5$ (d). After clusterization of the enhancers using the k-means algorithm, the silhouette score was computed for each enhancer vector. For each k-means clusterization corresponding to each panel, clusters are represented with different colors. A silhouette score can range from -1 to 1 with -1 indicating a possible assignment of the enhancer vector to the wrong cluster, 0 indicating that the vector is close to the boundary between two clusters, and 1 indicating that the vector is far away from the boundary between two clusters. The silhouette score is calculated as $(b - a) / \max(a, b)$ where a is the mean intra-cluster distance and b the mean nearest-cluster distance for each sample as implemented in the scikit-learn silhouette score function. The red dashed lines represent the average silhouette score over all the enhancer vectors.

Fig. S2 %GC composition of enhancers in k-means clusters. Histogram of the %GC of the enhancers in the two clusters (represented with red and green colors) obtained from the k-means algorithm applied to the positional patterns of G+C along human enhancers.

Fig. S3 Localization of the enhancers from the two classes. (a) Proportion of enhancers from class 1 (left) and 2 (right) located in 3' UTR, 5' UTR, intergenic regions, transcription termination sites (TTS), intronic regions, non-coding and coding exons, and promoter regions. (b) Density distribution of distances to transcription start sites (TSSs) for enhancers from class 1 (red) and class 2 (green).

Fig. S4 DNA shape patterns at enhancers (to be continued). Features associated with human enhancers from class 1 and class 2 are represented in red and green, respectively. **a-j** Average DNA shape values (y-axis; full lines) along the $\pm 2,000$ bp DNA sequences centered at enhancer mid-points (x-axis) for DNA shape features buckle (a), opening (b), ProT (c), rise (d), roll (e), shear (f), shift (g), slide (h), stagger (i), and tilt (j). Shadowed areas represent the 90% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Fig. S4 Continued.

Fig. S5 Normalized %GC and DNA shape patterns at enhancers (to be continued). Features associated with human enhancers from class 1 and class 2 are represented in red and green, respectively. Distribution of the normalized average %GC (a) and DNA shape values (y-axis) along the $\pm 2,000$ bp DNA sequences centered at enhancer mid-points (x-axis). DNA shapes considered are buckle (b), HeIT (c), MGW (d), opening (e), ProT (f), rise (g), roll (h), shear (i), shift (j), slide (k), stagger (l), stretch (m), and tilt (n).

Fig. S5 Continued.

Fig. S6 DNA shapes from shuffled enhancer sequences. DNA shape values for HelT (a), MGW (b), ProT (c), and Roll (d) computed using the DNASHapeR tool from shuffled sequences around class 1 (red) and class 2 (green) enhancers.

Fig. S7 *G+C content of promoters associated to each class of enhancers.* We extracted sequences spanning 500 bp around the start of genes associated to class 1 and class 2 enhancers (based on FANTOM5 + JEME associations) and computed GC content using the GC function of Biopython (median = 59.04 and 62.14 for promoters associated to respectively class 1 and class 2 enhancers, Wilcoxon test p -value $< 2.2e-16$).

Fig. S8 Human enhancers and genome segmentation. Histograms of the proportion of human enhancers (y-axis) in class 1 (red) and class 2 (green) lying within genome segments (x-axis) as annotated by combined results of ChromHMM and Segway on human lymphoblastoid (GM12878; **a**), cervical cancer (HeLa-S3; **b**), liver carcinoma (Hep G2; **c**), umbilical vein endothelial (HUVEC; **d**), and chronic myelogenous leukemia (K562; **e**) cell lines from the ENCODE project. Statistical significance (Bonferroni-corrected Fisher exact test p -value < 0.01) of enrichment for enhancers from a specific class is indicated by '**'.

Fig. S9 Enhancer activation upon MTB infection. Stacked histogram of the fraction of human enhancers (y-axis) from class 1 and class 2 predicted to be activated (white), inhibited (blue), or with unchanged activity (grey). Predictions were obtained using genomic segments predicted by ChromHMM on human dendritic cells before and after infection with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Fig. S10 *Enrichment of enhancers from a single class within chromatin loops.* For each chromatin loop predicted in HeLa-S3 (a), HMEC (b), HUVEC (c), IMR90 (d), K562 (e), KBM7 (f), and NHEK (g) cell lines, we computed the p -value of the Binomial test to assess enrichment for enhancers from a single class. The plots compare the density (y-axis) of p -values for Binomial tests (x-axis) applied to class 1 and 2 enhancers (plain lines) and 1,000 random assignments of class labels to the enhancers (dashed lines).

Fig. S11 Organization of enhancers within chromatin loops. Density (y-axis) of distances (x-axis) between enhancers and chromatin loop centers/anchors. The distances were normalized by the lengths of the loops. Enhancers at the center of the loops were found at distance 0.0 while enhancers at chromatin loops boundaries/anchors were found at distance 0.5. Results associated with class 1 and class 2 enhancers are depicted in red and green, respectively. HeLa-S3 (a), HMEC (b), HUVEC (c), IMR90 (d), K562 (e), KBM7 (f), and NHEK (g) cell lines were considered. In all cell types tested except HeLa-S3, class 1 enhancers were evenly distributed within the chromatin loops whereas enhancers from class 2 were observed to be situated close to the loop boundaries.